

Planning for More-than-Human Waterfronts: GIS-Based Habitat Suitability Modelling of Urban Kittiwake Nesting on the River Tyne

Andrew Schendl^{*1}, Mingyu Zhu^{†2}, Ayse Ozbil Torun^{‡1}, Bing Zhai^{§3} and Jiayi Jin^{¶1}

¹School of Architecture and Built Environment, Northumbria University

²School of Social and Political Sciences, University of Glasgow

³School of Computer Science, Northumbria University

GISRUK 2026

Summary

Urban waterfronts are increasingly shaped by the need to balance heritage conservation, economic vitality, and environmental responsibility. Along the River Tyne in Newcastle–Gateshead, the world’s most inland and urbanised colony of black-legged Kittiwakes (*Rissa tridactyla*) nests within a historic quayside that supports intensive tourism, leisure, and regeneration, generating persistent conflict related to noise, fouling, and building maintenance. This study develops a GIS-based habitat suitability framework to inform planning and policy responses to human–wildlife interactions, modelling presence-only nesting records as a function of environmental and built-form indicators using a hierarchical hexagonal grid and maximum entropy. The results identify clear spatial patterns of nesting suitability structured by waterfront morphology, building height and materials, vegetation cover, and infrastructure intensity, revealing numerous currently unoccupied but highly suitable locations. By anticipating where nesting is likely to emerge and how planning interventions may alter habitat conditions, the approach supports more proactive, place-sensitive decision-making. The study demonstrates how GIS can contribute to more-than-human urban planning by embedding ecological considerations into everyday spatial governance of heritage-rich waterfronts.

KEYWORDS: Urban ecology, More-than-human urbanism, Human–wildlife conflict, Habitat suitability modelling, Heritage and regeneration

1 Introduction

Along the River Tyne in Newcastle and Gateshead, UK, an exceptional urban ecological phenomenon unfolds each spring. Thousands of black-legged Kittiwakes (*Rissa tridactyla*) arrive not at their

*andrew.schendl@northumbria.ac.uk

†mingyu.zhu@glasgow.ac.uk

‡ayse.torun@northumbria.ac.uk

§bing.zhai@northumbria.ac.uk

¶jiayi.jin@northumbria.ac.uk

traditional coastal cliff habitats, but at concrete ledges, bridge structures, and building façades embedded deep within the urban core, with nesting recorded up to 17 kilometres inland from the coast (Turner, 2010). This population represents the world’s most inland and urbanised Kittiwake colony, documented through long-term monitoring and sustained breeding activity.

The emergence of this colony reflects broader environmental pressures affecting the species, including warming seas, increased storminess, and declining breeding success at natural coastal sites. Rather than dispersing along alternative coastal cliffs, Kittiwakes on the Tyne have adapted to human-made vertical structures that functionally replicate cliff environments. Shifts in rainfall distribution and storm intensity associated with climate change may further alter habitat suitability within such urban colonies, influencing nest success through increased exposure and disturbance to ledge-nesting birds unprotected by natural topography (Newell et al., 2015). While this adaptation has attracted attention as a striking example of urban wildlife resilience, it has also generated persistent conflict in a highly sensitive urban context characterised by historic waterfronts, intensive tourism, and ongoing regeneration (Newcastle City Council, 2019).

Unlike more general cases of urban biodiversity, the Tyne Kittiwake colony is spatially concentrated with a number of urban infrastructure and embedded within a dense urban core planning environment. Building maintenance, façade repair, scaffolding installation, adaptive reuse of heritage assets, and variations in traffic and pedestrian activity can all influence nesting behaviour, often unintentionally. These interactions reveal a critical gap between ecological understanding and urban planning practice, where planning decisions routinely reshape habitat conditions without explicit consideration of non-human urban inhabitants.

This study developed a GIS-based habitat suitability modelling framework tailored to urban environments and applied to Kittiwake urban nesting. By analysing the relationship between presence-only nesting observations and environmental and built-form indicators using a hierarchical hexagonal grid system, the study identifies both occupied and potentially suitable but currently unoccupied locations. The approach demonstrates how GIS-based modelling can support anticipatory planning for urban biodiversity in heritage-rich, intensively used waterfronts, contributing to more informed and inclusive decision-making in cities understood as shared, more-than-human environments.

2 Methods

This study adopted a spatially explicit, urban-scale habitat suitability modelling framework that integrates presence-only species distribution with fine-grained urban environmental and built-form indicators using a hexagonal grid system and maximum entropy modelling. By adopting an H3 hexagonal tessellation as a unifying spatial unit, the approach enables consistent aggregation of heterogeneous urban datasets while mitigating spatial bias inherent in point-based ecological records. The framework is specifically designed for small-sample, presence-only urban wildlife data and prioritises interpretability and transferability for urban planning and conservation decision-making.

2.1 Spatial framework

Urban Kittiwake nest locations were derived from annual breeding census surveys conducted by local ornithologists, providing systematic records of confirmed nesting sites along the River Tyne, including major quayside structures in Newcastle–Gateshead. The presence locations were then aggregated to a hierarchical hexagonal grid using the H3 spatial indexing system (Bousquin, 2021), for the following reasons. First, hexagonal tessellation reduces directional bias and edge effects relative to square grids, which is advantageous for species distribution modelling. Second, the hierarchical structure enables explicit and reproducible control of spatial resolution. Third, H3 provides a neutral spatial unit for integrating heterogeneous urban datasets, including point observations, building footprints, linear infrastructure, and raster-derived environmental indicators. More specifically, the grid resolution 11 (approximately 0.0023 km² per cell) was selected as a compromise between ecological relevance, representation of urban morphology, and data sparsity (Wisiz et al., 2008). At this resolution, each cell represents a plausible nesting environment rather than an individual structure or an overly generalised urban block.

In total, there are 17 presence cells containing confirmed nesting activity along with 14,084 background cells within 500m of water bodies containing at least one building. It reflects areas accessible to Kittiwakes along the river corridor but not necessarily occupied, thereby avoiding unrealistic contrasts between presence and other urban environments.

2.2 Habitat suitability modelling

Habitat suitability was modelled using maximum entropy (MaxEnt), a machine-learning approach designed for presence-only species distribution modelling (Phillips and Dudík, 2008). MaxEnt was selected due to the absence of reliable absence data and the small number of confirmed nesting locations. Unlike classification-based approaches requiring balanced presence–absence samples, MaxEnt estimates the most uniform probability distribution subject to constraints derived from environmental conditions at presence locations, making it well-suited to urban wildlife studies with uneven observation effort (Elith et al., 2011).

An initial pool of 19 candidate predictors was assembled spanning four broad categories:

- built-form characteristics (building footprint density, wall material, building height),
- infrastructure intensity (road network density),
- environmental proximity (distance to water, greenspace, agricultural land, residential areas, and industrial areas),
- interpolated atmospheric and environmental factors (wind speed, temperature, humidity, sound level, NO₂, CO, PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, O₃).

Predictors were screened for high collinearity (Pearson $|r| > 0.7$) and limited variance, resulting in a six-variable model. This was further refined using permutation importance analysis, producing a final model with five predictors: *distance to water*, *the Normalised Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI)*, *road density*, *average building height*, and *dominant wall material type* as shown in Table

1 . Mean vegetation cover was represented by NDVI, a measure of vegetation greenness calculated from Sentinel-2 imagery data as equation 1:

$$\text{NDVI} = \frac{\text{NIR} - \text{Red}}{\text{NIR} + \text{Red}} \quad (1)$$

where NIR and Red refer to near-infrared and red spectral bands, respectively. Euclidean distance to the nearest water body was measured from each cell centroid. Built-form characteristics were extracted from individual building datasets and aggregated to the grid. These included average building height and dominant wall material type. Road density was calculated using OpenStreetMap data as the total length of road segments within each hexagon (km) normalised by cell area (km²). All predictors were standardised prior to modelling.

Model outputs were generated using the complementary log–log (cloglog) transformation, which provides predictions interpretable as estimates of probability of presence and facilitates intuitive spatial interpretation for planning and conservation applications. Cells lacking buildings were assigned zero suitability.

Table 1: Predictors type and data source

Type	Name	Source
Environmental	NDVI	Sentinel-2
	Distance to Water	CEH Land Cover Map
Built-form	Building height	Verisk UKBuildings
	Wall material	
	Road density	OpenStreetMap

2.3 Model evaluation

Given the small presence sample (n=17), model performance was evaluated using jackknife validation rather than conventional train–test splits. This approach iteratively withholds each presence location, allowing robust assessment without sacrificing a substantial proportion of the data. Model performance was assessed using the area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC). Permutation importance quantified relative variable contributions by measuring reductions in AUC when each predictor was randomised.

3 Results

The MaxEnt habitat suitability model demonstrated strong predictive performance despite the small presence sample (AUC = 0.965, SD = 0.063; jackknife AUC = 0.983, SD = 0.041), correctly classifying 16 of the 17 confirmed nesting cells. Permutation importance analysis identified distance to water as the dominant predictor, followed by vegetation cover (NDVI), road density, average building height, and dominant wall material type.

Figure 1: Distribution of key predictors across available urban locations and confirmed nest sites.

Model coefficients indicated strong selection for locations proximate to water, characterised by low vegetation cover, higher road density, and taller buildings, particularly those constructed with brick or stone façades. These patterns are consistent with the adaptation of Kittiwakes to urban environments that functionally replicate their natural cliff-nesting habitats.

Comparison between confirmed nest sites and available urban locations revealed clear separation across all key predictors (Figure 1). Nest sites were associated with significantly taller buildings (17-25m or 4-6 storeys), substantially shorter distances to water (less than 100 m), higher road density (between 55-170 km/km²), and markedly lower NDVI values (lower than 0.1) relative to available cells. In particular, distance to water exhibited minimal overlap between occupied and available locations, reinforcing its role as the primary constraint on urban nesting. Vegetation cover at nest sites was consistently low, while available locations spanned a broad NDVI range, indicating strong avoidance of vegetated environments. Road density was higher at nest sites, reflecting the concentration of nesting activity within highly urbanised, infrastructure-dense waterfront areas rather than low-intensity or suburban contexts.

Spatial predictions across the Newcastle–Gateshead urban area identified 123 hexagonal cells with suitability values ≥ 0.5 (Figure 2). These high-suitability cells were strongly clustered along the Tyne quayside corridor and exhibited a mean building height of 21.7 m. The majority of highly suitable locations were currently unoccupied, indicating substantial capacity for future colony expansion within the existing urban fabric.

Figure 2: Predicted habitat suitability probability map with confirmed nesting sites highlighted in red

4 Conclusion

This study demonstrates how urban wildlife habitat suitability can be modelled in a way that is both methodologically robust and directly relevant to urban planning practice. By modelling presence-only species observations with fine-grained urban environmental and built-form indicators using a hexagonal spatial framework, the proposed approach moves beyond species-centric prediction towards actionable spatial insight for cities managing human–wildlife coexistence.

The results highlight that Kittiwake nesting in Newcastle–Gateshead is not randomly distributed across the urban fabric, but strongly structured by urban form and waterfront morphology. Nesting sites are associated with proximity to water, taller buildings with hard surfaces, higher road density, and low vegetation cover. Together, these characteristics indicate the functional substitution of natural cliff habitats by dense, vertical waterfront architecture. Crucially, these preferences intersect with urban strategic planning processes that are routinely shaped through building alterations, waterfront redevelopment, and public realm interventions. The identification of numerous unoccupied yet highly suitable locations along the Tyne quayside suggests that future colony expansion is likely to occur within existing urban areas rather than through outward spread, thereby increasing the potential for human–wildlife conflict if such growth is not proactively managed.

From an urban planning perspective, the model provides a proactive tool for anticipating where nesting is likely to emerge, enabling earlier and more targeted interventions. Rather than reacting to nesting once conflicts arise, planners and conservation practitioners can use suitability maps to identify specific buildings or zones where mitigation, accommodation, or deterrence strategies may be most appropriate. This supports a shift from reactive conflict management towards anticipatory planning for urban biodiversity, particularly in post-industrial waterfronts undergoing regeneration (Jin et al., 2026).

Methodologically, the study illustrates the value of combining GIS-based spatial frameworks, interpretable machine-learning models, and explicit validation of model behaviour through comparison with observed urban environments. The approach is transferable to other urban wildlife contexts characterised by limited presence data and complex built environments, offering a scalable template for integrating ecological considerations into spatial planning workflows. Overall, the findings reinforce the role of GIS not only as an analytical tool, but as a bridge between urban ecological processes and planning decision-making in rapidly transforming cities.

5 Acknowledgment

This paper is the output of the 'Navigating Urban Enologies: Mapping the Habitation Patterns and Socio-ecological Dynamics of Kittiwakes along the River Tyne' project (<https://research.northumbria.ac.uk/nue/>).

It is funded by the Arts and Humanities Research Council (AHRC, #UKRI271) under the 'Design Exchange Partnerships: design the green transition scheme'. We thank our external expert and the ornithologist, Dan Turner, for sharing his expertise on Tyne kittiwakes and for guiding aspects of the research.

6 Biography

Andrew Schendl is the Research Assistant for the Navigating Urban Ecologies project. He is a PhD student in the ENVISION Doctoral Training Partnership at Bangor University, within the School of Environmental and Natural Sciences. Andrew's research focuses on understanding human movement dynamics within urban environments.

Dr Mingyu Zhu is a Research Associate for the Navigating Urban Ecologies project. His research interests encompass the design, construction, and operation of the urban built environment, with a focus on GeoBIM, Model-Based Systems Engineering (MBSE), and Human-Computer Interaction (HCI).

Dr Jiayi Jin is the Project Lead of the Navigating Urban Ecologies project. She is an Assistant Professor in Architecture and Urban Studies at the School of Architecture and Built Environment, Northumbria University. Her research focuses on inclusive cities and the use of digital applications and co-creation methods to support the green transition.

Dr Ayse Ozbil Torun is the Project Co-Lead of the Navigating Urban Ecologies project. She is an Associate Professor in Architecture and Urban Studies at the School of Architecture and Built Environment, Northumbria University. Her research interests mainly lie in the fields of spatial modelling and urban form analysis using space syntax techniques.

Dr Bing Zhai is the Project Co-Lead of the Navigating Urban Ecologies project. He is an Assistant Professor in Artificial Intelligence at the School of Computer Science, Northumbria University. His research agenda is to develop practical AI tools to solve time-series data challenges in real-world applications.

References

- Bousquin, J. (2021). Discrete global grid systems as scalable geospatial frameworks for characterizing coastal environments. *Environmental Modelling & Software*, 146, 105210, <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2021.105210>.
- Elith, J., Phillips, S. J., Hastie, T., Dudík, M., Chee, Y. E., & Yates, C. J. (2011). A statistical explanation of maxent for ecologists. *Diversity and distributions*, 17(1), 43–57, <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1472-4642.2010.00725.x>.
- Jin, J., Laing, R., & Zhu, M. (2026). Co-mapping future scenarios and uncertainties amid climate crisis: A collective study of coastal towns and the port of tyne. *Journal of Urban Management*, 15(1), 324–342, <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jum.2025.07.002>.
- Newcastle City Council (2019). Kittiwakes – bridging the tyne. Available at: https://www.newcastle.gov.uk/sites/default/files/2019-01/kittiwakes_-_bridging_the_tyne_web.pdf (accessed March 2026).
- Newell, M., Wanless, S., Harris, M. P., & Daunt, F. (2015). Effects of an extreme weather event on

seabird breeding success at a North Sea colony. *Marine Ecology Progress Series*, 532, 257–268, <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps11329>.

Phillips, S. J. & Dudík, M. (2008). Modeling of species distributions with maxent: new extensions and a comprehensive evaluation. *Ecography*, 31(2), 161–175, <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1111/j.0906-7590.2008.5203.x>.

Turner, D. (2010). Counts and breeding success of black-legged kittiwakes *rissa tridactyla* nesting on man-made structures along the river tyne, northeast england, 1994-2009. *Seabird*, 23, 111–126. Available at: <https://seabirdgroup.org.uk/journals/seabird-23/seabird-23-111.pdf> (accessed March 2026).

Wisz, M. S., Hijmans, R. J., Li, J., Peterson, A. T., Graham, C. H., Guisan, A., & Group, N. P. S. D. W. (2008). Effects of sample size on the performance of species distribution models. *Diversity and distributions*, 14(5), 763–773, <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1472-4642.2008.00482.x>.